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DISCOURSE MARKER SO, IT'S FUNCTION AND CHANGES IN TRANSLATION

Tursunboyeva Farangis

Bukhara State Pedagogical institute

Student of 2nd course

Introduction. The role of discourse markers in linguistics is incomparable. Each of discourse marker has its own role, importance and field of application. This article covers the functional signs of the discourse marker "SO", its equivalents in Uzbek, and changes in translation. This article also provides several examples of how the discourse marker "so" is used.

Discourse markers are words or phrases that simply add attraction to a sentence and that are not part of sentence itself. When we remove the discourse markers from the sentences, if no meaning changes in the sentences, then they are considered a discourse markers.

We know that spices and salts are not seen in salads, but they have their own special taste. Discourse markers also give a special charm to the sentences, even if they do not have much importance. Examples of discourse markers include words and phrases like 'however', 'on the other hand', 'because', 'firstly', 'so,'well' and 'you

Methodology. History of SO. The word "so" has been used as a discourse marker since the 70s of the last century. Also, many scholars have studied "so" along with other discourse markers. These include the following scholars: Deborah Schiffrin (1987), Bruce Fraser(1999-2006),Laurel Brinton(1996-2008),Gisle Andersen(2001-20017), Alexandra Jucker(1993-2002).

Among these, Deborah initiates the study of so discourse markers. Deborah Schiffrin, a leading discourse analyst, studied discourse markers extensively in her book *Discourse Markers* (1987). She analyzed “so” as discourse markers, examining their role in structuring conversations and managing coherence.

The functions of so discourse marker. Each discourse marker has its own function that helps to find out what that marker refers to and in what sense it is used. Below are the functional signs of the discourse marker.

1. In expressing the result.
2. In continuing the sentence.
3. for emphasis
4. Conclusion
5. reformulation/Resumption
6. condition
7. Mild surprise
8. Avoidance or Evasion

Each Uzbek equivalent of the discourse marker so has a functional marker. Below you can see the equivalents of so and their functional signs.

1. Shuning uchun, shu bois, natijada, shu sababli-in expressing the result
2. Xo‘sh, yaxshi, demak-in continuing the sentence
3. Juda, nihoyatda, o‘ta-for emphasis
4. Demak, xulosa qilib aytganda-Conclusin
5. Xullas, aytmoqchi, demak-reformulation/Resumption
6. Agar, bo‘lsa, taqdirdagina-condition
7. Demak, qarangi-mild surprise
8. Nima bo‘pti, keyin nima-Avoidance or evasion

Result. Correct translation of the discourse marker’s meaning and its artisticization certainly depend on the translator’s thinking. Khaled Hosseini’s *Kite Runner* can be as an example, we can see the changes in the translation process and what words the translator used instead of the so discourse marker. In a directly

translated book translator chose not to translate the so discursive marker in some case. The translation of “so” is given and one of its Uzbek equivalents is chosen. Let’s take a few sentences from the original and the translation of this work and consider its functional signs and which equivalent in the Uzbek language is chosen.

"So he’s not violent" Rahim Khan said. (Khaled Hosseini’s Kite Runner page 17)

Translation: "Sal muloyimroq yigit bo‘lsa nima qipti ?"(Khaled Hosseini’s Kite Runner page 18)

Analyze. If this sentence is directly translated into Uzbek, it will be translated as "demak u zo‘ravon emas". but the translator Rustam Jabbarov translated it in a completely different way. Rustam Jabbarov translated this sentence like this "sal muloyimroq yigit bo‘lsa nima qipti?" In this sentence, in order to soften the sentence "he is not a violent", the translator uses the word "gentler" as a synonym for it, and the discourse marker is used as a synonym for the word "sal". In this sentence, the discourse marker so means to summarize the thought, but the translator equated it with the word "sal" in Uzbek. In this case, the translator adapted the meaning of so to the text so that the translation came out beautifully, which shows the skill of the translator. In linguistics have grammar transformations and when you change the sentence from positive to negative it is called to interrogative transformation (question formation).

Discussion: "I was stunned. That particular point, so obvious it was utterly stupid, hadn’t even occurred to me. (Khaled Hosseini’s Kite Runner page 27)

Translation: "Demak yozganlarim bir pulga qimmat ekan-da!" (Khaled Hosseini’s Kite Runner page 24)

Explanation: "If we analyze so in this sentence, the translator translated the above sentence as follows: "Demak yozganlarim bir pulga qimmat ekan-da!" If we translate directly "men esankirab qoldim. Bu mutlaqo ahmoqlik ekanligi aniq edi, hatto xayolimga ham kelmagan edi". When we compare these two translations, the first one translates so means and uses the Uzbek inference equivalent. And in the second sentence, it is not necessary to translate so and it is omitted. The translator preferred to combine several sentences to make one whole sentence and made the sentence more

beautiful by giving the meaning with a phrase. When a sentence is followed by a corresponding phrase without direct translation, it is called a " clause-to-phrase" in linguistics.

"Oh"he said."Wah wah!So,if I understand, you'll study several years to earn degree,then you'll get a chatti job like mine,one you could just as easily land today,on the small change that your degree might someday help you get... discovered."(Khaled Hosseini's Kite Runner page 113)

Translation: – Qiziq, – yelka qisdi otam. – O'qish uchun bir necha umringni sarflab, keyin yana pul topish uchun menga o'xshab qora ish topasanmi? Unaqada o'qishning nima keragi bor?(Khaled Hosseini's Kite Runner page 82)

Explanation: This sentence has the discourse marker SO, but the translator has modified it rather than translating it directly. Instead of "oh" he said", the translator uses the word "qiziq" because here the word "oh"comes in the meaning of surprise. The sentences " so if I understand" was preferred not to be translated at all, and the omissin was observed in this place.

Conclusion. As discourse marker has a role, the role of so is significant in translation. In the process of translation, one of the equivalents of so is chosen, but in some situations, a word completely alien to so can be taken as a synonym. This depends on the translator's ingenuity and word selection skills. In the process of translating any work the attractiveness of the work and how much it will be liked by the reader also depends on the skill of the translator.

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